

Using rice cultivar mixtures: a sustainable approach for managing diseases and increasing yield

N.P. Castilla, C.M. Vera Cruz, and T.W. Mew, IRRI; and Y. Zhu, The Phytopathology Laboratory of Yunnan Province, Yunnan Agricultural University, Kunming, Yunnan 650201, China. Email: n.castilla@cgiar.org

The adoption of modern rice cultivars has increased annual production in the past three decades by 2.4% per annum and average yield by 71% (Khush and Virk 2002). Modern cultivars continue to replace thousands of traditional cultivars (Chang 1994). Although the number of landraces used in breeding modern cultivars has increased in the same period (Hossain et al 2003), many modern cultivars share the same genetic background (Chang 1994), which has contributed to the instability of resistance against several rice diseases with high epidemic potential.

A sustainable approach in managing modern cultivars is functional diversification. Functional biodiversity (Schmidt 1978) is based on the principle of using cultivars with diversified functions to limit the development of diseases. A growing number of studies show that, in natural ecosystems, functional diversity leads to higher stability (Petchey and Gaston 2002). This means that, in agroecosystems, haphazard cultivar mixtures do not necessarily control diseases and increase yield and that prolonging the useful life of resistance genes and increasing crop productivity may be achieved by taking into account the functional differences in disease resistance and other agronomic traits of cultivars. Such functional diversification can be achieved by using multilines and cultivar mixtures (Wolfe 1985).

The usefulness of mixtures, whether multilines or cultivar mixtures, for disease management has been well demonstrated for rusts and barley powdery mildews of cere-

als (Finckh et al 2000, Mundt 2002). Multilines are mixtures of genotypically identical lines (near-isogenic lines) that differ only in a specific disease or pest resistance gene (Browning and Frey 1981). Multiline cultivars of rice are widely used to prevent the breakdown of resistance against blast in Japan, where the first registered rice multiline was released in 1995 (Koizumi 2001). Cultivar mixtures refer to mixtures of cultivated varieties growing simultaneously on the same parcel of land with no attempt to breed for phenotypic uniformity (Mundt 2002). The use of cultivar mixtures is considered to be more practical and requires less investment than the use of multilines because there is no need to breed new cultivars. This can be easily implemented by resource-poor farmers in developing countries—all that they have to do is mix existing cultivars with favorable agronomic traits and performance. Mixing existing cultivars with more diverse genetic backgrounds than multilines can enhance functional diversity and improve yield by providing more chances for positive interactions among cultivars. Moreover, this offers better opportunities for on-farm conservation of genetic resources by allowing farmers to grow traditional cultivars.

Farmers in subsistence farming communities grow several cultivars in a field or adjacent field as a strategy to cope with heterogeneous and uncertain ecological and socioeconomic conditions (Bellon 1996). The success of the large-scale farmer participatory experiment in Yunnan, China, in which traditional cultivars and hybrid rice are interplanted to control blast and increase yield (Zhu et al 2000), has contradicted the long-held assumption that cultivar mixtures should be restricted to low-input and small-scale rice production systems. This has provided new insights into the important components that can help ensure the success of using cultivar mixtures as a large-scale genetic diversification scheme in modern rice production systems.

This article reviews the current knowledge about the mechanisms that account for disease reduction and yield increase in cultivar mixtures of multiple crops. It discusses the various determinants in the adoption of cultivar mixtures and the prospects for and challenges in using cultivar mixtures as a functional diversification strategy.

Mechanisms for reducing disease intensity and increasing yield and yield stability

The underlying mechanisms behind the reduction in disease intensity and the increase in yield and

yield stability are relatively well understood in other crops (Mundt 2002). Much remains to be done in understanding the same concepts in rice cultivar mixtures, but it can be assumed that most of the mechanisms reported in mixtures of other crops could also operate in rice.

Mechanisms for disease reduction

Several review articles explain the various mechanisms by which cultivar mixtures reduce disease intensity (Mundt 2002).

Dilution effect. Disease is reduced in cultivar mixtures because of the increased distance between plants of the susceptible cultivar in the mixture (Browning and Frey 1969, Chin and Wolfe 1984). The presence of the resistant cultivar decreases the chance of the inoculum produced from the infected susceptible cultivar of landing on another susceptible cultivar. Most of the inoculum lands on the resistant cultivar, thus reducing the rate of disease increase.

Barrier effect. The resistant cultivar provides a physical barrier that restricts the movement of the inoculum from the susceptible cultivar (Browning and Frey 1969). For mixtures of differentially susceptible cultivars (i.e., both components are susceptible to different races of the pathogen), plants of cultivar A serve as a barrier for the race that attacks cultivar B, and vice versa.

Induced resistance. This occurs when races that are nonvirulent on a cultivar induce the plant's defense response mechanisms. As a consequence, any virulent race (genetically different isolate of the same pathogen that would normally infect the plant) invading exactly the same area of the plant cannot cause infection (Chin and Wolfe 1984).

Competition among pathogen races. The diversity of pathogen genotypes is expected to be higher in cultivar mixtures than in monoculture, thus increasing the chance of interactions and competition between pathogen races (Garrett and Mundt 1999). Competition among different virulent races may prevent a certain race from dominating and overcoming host resistance in cultivar mixtures, thus reducing disease in the mixtures.

Mechanisms for increasing yield and yield stability

Cultivar mixtures can have a higher yield and more yield stability than pure stands of the components (Finckh et al 2000). Yield advantages are more commonly observed in mixtures that have decreased

disease intensity (Finckh and Mundt 1992, Mundt et al 1995). Aside from the reduction in disease, several mechanisms are believed to account for the increase in yield and yield stability in cultivar mixtures.

Complementarity. The yield benefit of cultivar mixtures may be a function of complementary resource use above- and belowground (Willey 1979). As in interspecific mixtures, a yield advantage occurs when cultivar components differ in their use of resources in space and time in such a way that overall use of resources is better than when components are grown separately. Complementarity usually occurs when component cultivars have different growth durations because the demand on resources occurs at different times (Fukai and Trenbath 1993).

Compensation. Compensation usually happens between cultivars with different competitive abilities (Willey 1979). It occurs when the yield of one component increases while the other decreases without affecting the overall yield of the mixture (Khalifa and Qualset 1974). Compensatory tillering by resistant plants was observed when disease occurred early in the season (Brophy and Mundt 1991) and even in mixtures where disease intensity was not affected (Mundt et al 1995). Compensation was also observed in cultivar mixtures where the components differed in plant height (Khalifa and Qualset 1974).

Facilitation. Facilitation is the positive effect of plants on the establishment or growth of other plants (Garcia-Barrios 2002). A component cultivar may benefit another component directly by improving microclimate, providing physical support or windbreaks, and ameliorating harsh environmental conditions, or indirectly by providing protection from other pests and diseases, and improving water-holding capacity (Callaway 1995, Garcia-Barrios 2002). Although rarely quantified, a form of facilitation observed in rice cultivar mixtures is the higher resistance to lodging of tall cultivars in mixtures than in monoculture.

Major determinants in growing rice cultivar mixtures

Various biological and socioeconomic factors must be considered in the choice of cultivars to be used in mixtures and their deployment in space and time. These factors and their interrelationships are summarized in the figure.

Choice of cultivars

Functional diversity of cultivars. An important prerequisite in using mixtures is the diversity of cultivars to be included in terms of functions, such as resistance to the prevailing populations of the pathogen, resource use, and other agronomic traits. The functional diversity approach can help reduce diseases and increase yield. Advances in genomics

Interrelationships among some factors that affect the adoption of rice cultivar mixtures.

and the recent completion of the rice genome may help determine the functions of genes and predict the performance of both traditional and modern cultivars to be included in the mixtures (Leung et al 2003).

Yield potential. The yield potential of the cultivars may be more important in some areas where farmers are more concerned with maximizing yield than reducing disease. Although disease reduction is expected to increase yield, a more preferable option is to choose at least one cultivar with high potential yield to increase the chances of attaining high yield.

Other traits preferred by farmers. Rice farmers do not always consider disease resistance or yield as the sole criterion in choosing cultivars. In areas where modern cultivars are widely adopted, market demand has increasingly become the most important selection criterion (Friis-Hansen 2000). Farmers may prefer to combine cultivars that fulfill different requirements as generally observed in rice-growing areas where multiple traditional cultivars are grown (Bellon 1996)—e.g. good eating quality for cultivar A and high yield potential for cultivar B. Most farmers, particularly in modern rice production systems, would prefer to mix cultivars that are similar in crop duration and phenotype to facilitate crop establishment and maintenance, harvesting, and marketing of harvested grains.

Spatial deployment of cultivar mixtures

Proportion of cultivars. Various studies suggest that the mean level of resistance of all components with respect to the population of the pathogen has a stronger effect on disease intensity than the number of components (Finckh et al 2000). Increasing the optimum proportion of resistant cultivars is expected to increase the efficacy of the cultivar mixture because of the dilution effect. However, the proportion of the resistant cultivars is dictated not only by the expected effects on disease intensity but also by its effects on yield and whether it can fulfill the requirements of farmers. Farmers who produce rice mainly for the market may prefer to grow a higher proportion of the cultivar that commands a higher price. In seed mixtures, the desired proportion may depend on the eating quality of the product. Furthermore, plant type may be a consideration. For example, in mixtures composed of cultivars that differ in height, increasing the proportion of the taller cultivar may adversely affect the growth and yield of the shorter cultivar.

Planting or spatial pattern of cultivars. In several cases, the efficacy of cultivar mixtures depends not only on the proportion of susceptible and resistant components but also on the planting pattern. If the initial disease is distributed randomly or uniformly, such as the foliar diseases caused by wind-dispersed pathogens, the efficacy of mixtures increases as the genotype unit area (GUA) decreases (Mundt et al 1996). GUA is the area occupied by an independent unit of host tissue of the same genotype. For cultivar mixtures to be effective against diseases, cultivars with the same level of resistance should not be adjacent to each other. A rice cultivar mixture in which the hills consist of seedlings belonging to different cultivars has a lower GUA than one with several rows of each cultivar alternating. Cultivar mixtures could be less effective for the control of diseases, such as bacterial blight, which is caused by a pathogen that is mainly dispersed by rain splash or water (Ahmed et al 1997). The inoculum dispersed by this mechanism usually lands close to the source plant; thus, rows of resistant plants cannot effectively serve as a barrier between rows of susceptible plants. Mixing seeds of a susceptible cultivar with those of other cultivars with functional resistance genes will result in reduced GUA and may effectively suppress bacterial blight.

Spatial pattern also affects yield and competitiveness of components in the mixture (Fernandez et al 2002). To improve yield, there is a need to consider a spatial pattern that would allow cultivars, especially those with varying phenotypes, to interact positively and compete less. Spatial pattern may, in part, be determined by its suitability to existing cropping practices, specifically with respect to crop establishment and harvesting.

Temporal deployment of cultivar mixtures

It may be necessary to change the composition of cultivar mixtures after a specific period of time. The use of saved seeds from one season to another may lead to a shift in the composition of cultivar mixtures due to the enhanced competitive ability of a component because of diseases (Alexander et al 1986). It may also decrease the productivity of cultivar mixtures even in the absence of disease (Khalifa and Qualset 1974). Changing the mixture composition after a given period could delay the shift of the population structure of the pathogen toward virulent races, which occurs after successive cultivation of the same cultivars. Another reason for changing the components is the change in

the preferences of farmers and consumers.

The most common methods of mixing rice cultivars and their advantages, disadvantages, and applications are shown in the table.

Prospects and challenges

The main challenge in the use of cultivar mixtures as a functional diversification scheme lies in the fact that designing a system for mixing cultivars is a dynamic process. It should be customized not only to the diseases and cultivars but also to the various biotic constraints and cropping practices of farmers in a specific area. Several research issues must be examined in designing an optimum system; these are the most important: (1) What cultivars should be combined? (2) What are the effects of certain proportions and planting patterns on major diseases and other biotic constraints and crop productivity? and (3) What are the mechanisms (i.e., ecological and genetic bases) behind disease reduction and yield increase? The next step is to analyze practical issues. A system for mixing cultivars must be designed to minimize anticipated difficulties in crop establishment, harvesting, and milling and marketing of grains that are usually associated with the adoption of cultivar mixtures. It is also important to quantify the costs and benefits to determine whether the benefits, such as those derived from the increase in yield and reduction in fungicide use, can offset additional costs. Farmers in Yunnan, China, incurred additional cost in transplanting and harvesting, but they continue to interplant cultivars because the economic benefits exceeded the costs (Leung et al 2003).

The prospects for using rice cultivar mixtures appear to be more promising now than decades ago because of the availability of several new approaches that are important in choosing the right combination and spatio-temporal deployment of cultivars. Recent advances in genomics, coupled with phenotyping, allow the selection of cultivars with defense genes effective against the population of pathogens in a given location. More importantly, these advances may help in the selection of component cultivars that are functionally diverse with respect to disease resistance and agronomic traits. Experimental designs and various analytical approaches can now be used to evaluate disease epidemics and interactions of cultivars in mixtures and, consequently, allow for a more efficient identification of a system that suppresses diseases and maximizes positive interactions among cultivars. Moreover, various farmer participatory methods can be

applied to ensure that a given system suits the social, cultural, and economic needs of farmers. Using a combination of these approaches, on-farm experiments are under way in China, the Philippines, and Indonesia to explore the use of rice cultivar mixtures.

References

- Ahmed HU, Finckh MR, Alfonso RF, Mundt CC. 1997. Epidemiological effect of gene deployment strategies on bacterial blight of rice. *Phytopathology* 87:66–70.
- Alexander HM, Roelfs AP, Cobbs G. 1986. Effects of disease and plant competition on yield in monoculture and mixtures of two wheat cultivars. *Plant Pathol.* 35:457–465.
- Bellon MR. 1996. The dynamics of infraspecific diversity: a conceptual framework at the farmer level. *Econ. Bot.* 50:26–39.
- Browning JA, Frey KJ. 1969. Multiline cultivars as a means of disease control. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 14:355–382.
- Browning JA, Frey KJ. 1981. The multiline concept in theory and practice. In: Jenkyn JF, Plumb RT, editors. *Strategies for the control of cereal disease*. Oxford: Blackwell Publications. p 37–46.
- Callaway RM. 1995. Positive interactions among plants. *Bot. Rev.* 61:306–349.
- Chang TT. 1994. The biodiversity crisis in Asian crop production and remedial measures. In: Peng CI, Chou CH, editors. *Biodiversity and terrestrial ecosystems*. Taipei: Institute of Botany, Academia Sinica. p 25–41.
- Chin KM, Wolfe MS. 1984. Selection on *Erysiphe graminis* in pure and mixed stands of barley. *Plant Pathol.* 33: 535–546.
- Fernandez ON, Vignolio OR, Requenses EC. 2002. Competition between corn (*Zea mays*) and Bermuda grass (*Cynodon dactylon*) in relation to crop plant arrangement. *Agronomie* 22:293–305.
- Finckh MR, Mundt CC. 1992. Stripe rust, yield, and plant competition in wheat cultivar mixtures. *Phytopathology* 82:905–913.
- Finckh MR, Gacek ES, Goyeau H, Lannou C, Merz U, Mundt CC, Munk L, Nadziak J, Newton AC, Vallavieille-Pope C, Wolfe MS. 2000. Cereal variety and species mixtures in practice, with emphasis on disease resistance. *Agronomie* 20:813–837.
- Friis-Hansen E. 2000. Farmers' management and use of crop genetic diversity in Tanzania. In: Almekinders C, De Boef W, editors. *Encouraging diversity. The conservation and development of plant genetic resources*. London: Intermediate Technology Publications. p 66–71.
- Fukai S, Trenbath BR. 1993. Processes determining intercrop productivity and yields of component crops. *Field Crops Res.* 34:247–271.
- Garcia-Barríos L. 2002. Plant-plant interactions in tropical agriculture. In: Vandermeer JH, editor. *Tropical agroecosystems*. Boca Raton, Florida: CRC Press. p 11–58.
- Garrett KA, Mundt CC. 1999. Epidemiology in mixed host populations. *Phytopathology* 89:984–990.
- Hossain M, Gollin D, Cabanilla V, Cabrera E, Johnson N, Khush GS, McLaren G. 2003. Crop genetic improvement

Method	Example of Spatial pattern	Advantages	Disadvantages	Applications
Random seed mixture	XOXOXOXO OOXOXOXO XOXOXOXO XOXOXOXO XOXOXOXO 1 susceptible: 1 resistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> May result in high disease control Facilitates crop establishment, management, and harvest if cultivars have the same height and maturity Can be easily adopted for both transplanted and direct-seeded rice 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional diversity may be low as cultivars may have similar genetic backgrounds Since seeds will have to be marketed as a mixture, proportion should take into account effect on eating and yield quality Cultivars should have the same phenotype and maturity 	<p>A 1:1 seed mixture of IR64, a susceptible cultivar with good eating quality, and a resistant line effectively reduced tungro in southern Philippines at high and low disease pressures (R. Cabunagan and I.R. Choi, IRRI, unpub. results)</p>
Single-row interplanting (interplanting one row of a susceptible cultivar between several rows of resistant cultivars)	XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX XXOX 1 susceptible: 4 resistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional diversity could be higher than in method 1 Disease control in the susceptible cultivar can be high, but lower than in the seed mixture Cultivars with different uses, height, and maturity can be mixed Lodging of taller cultivar can be minimized 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Transplanting and harvesting can be laborious and time-consuming if cultivars differ in maturity 	<p>Interplanting susceptible glutinous cultivars with resistant hybrid rice cultivars (Zhu et al 002) was done in Yunnan and Sichuan, China to control blast</p>
Alternate-row interplanting (alternating several rows of susceptible and resistant cultivars)	XXXOXXXXO XXXOXXXXO XXXOXXXXO XXXOXXXXO XXXOXXXXO 3 susceptible: 3 resistant	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Cultivars with different uses, height, and maturity can be mixed Lodging of taller cultivar may be minimized but probably with lower efficacy than in method 2 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disease control can be lower than in methods 1 and 2, especially if highly susceptible cultivars are used Transplanting and harvesting can be laborious and time-consuming if cultivars differ in maturity Proportion of cultivars should consider effect on competition between cultivars that differ in height and maturity 	<p>Evaluated for efficacy against blast in upland rice in Lampung Province, Indonesia, using susceptible modern cultivars with high yield potential and resistant traditional cultivars with low yield potential; initial results showed no reduction in neck blast relative to monoculture of susceptible cultivar; future trials will consider modern cultivars with moderate susceptibility to blast</p>

- in developing countries: overview and summary. In: Evenson RE, Gollin D, editors. *Crop variety improvement and its effect on productivity. The impact of international agricultural research*. Wallingford, Oxon: CAB International. p 7-38.
- Khalifa MA, Qualset CO. 1974. Intergenotypic competition between tall and dwarf wheats. I. In mechanical mixtures. *Crop Sci.* 14:795-799.
- Khush GS, Virk PS. 2002. Rice improvement: past, present and future. In: Kang, MS, editor. *Crop improvement: challenges in the twenty-first century*. New York: Food Products Press. p 17-42.
- Koizumi S. 2001. Rice blast control with multilines in Japan. In: Mew TW, Borromeo E, Hardy B, editors. *Exploiting biodiversity for sustainable pest management. Proceedings of the impact symposium on exploiting biodiversity for sustainable pest management, Kunming China, 21-23 Aug 2000. Los Baños (Philippines): International Rice Research Institute.* p 143-157.
- Leung H, Zhu, Y, Revilla-Molina I, Fan JX, Chen H, Pangga I, Vera Cruz C, Mew TW. 2003. Using genetic diversity to achieve sustainable rice disease management. *Plant Dis.* 87:1156-1169.
- Mundt CC. 2002. Use of multiline cultivars and cultivar mixtures for disease management. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 40: 381-410.
- Mundt CC, Brophy LS, Schmitt ME. 1995. Choosing crop cultivars and mixtures under high versus low disease pressure: a case study with wheat. *Crop Prot.* 14:509-515.
- Mundt CC, Brophy LS, Kolar SC. 1996. Effect of genotype unit number and spatial arrangement on severity of yellow rust in wheat cultivar mixtures. *Plant Pathol.* 45:215-222.
- Mundt CC, Browning JA. 1985. Development of crown rust epidemics in genetically diverse oat populations: effect of genotype unit area. *Phytopathology* 75:607-610.
- Petchey OL, Gaston KL. 2002. Functional diversity (FD), species richness and community composition. *Ecol. Lett.* 5:402-411.
- Willey RW. 1979. Intercropping – its importance and research needs. Part 1. Competition and yield advantages. *Field Crops Abstr.* 32:1-10.
- Wolfe MS. 1985. The current status and prospects of multiline cultivars and variety mixtures for disease resistance. *Annu. Rev. Phytopathol.* 23:251-273.
- Zhu Y, Chen H, Fan JH, Wang Y, Li Y, Chen J, Fan JX, Yang S, Hu L, Leung H, Mew TW, Teng PS, Wang Z, Mundt CC. 2000. Genetic diversity and disease control in rice. *Nature* 406:718-722.
-

GUIDELINES ON SUBMITTING ELECTRONIC FILES TO IRRN

1. Authors should submit separate text and table files in MS Word. Text files should not be formatted. For text files, authors should use Arial 12 points, left alignment, no justification, and double space with only one space between sentences and no extra space between paragraphs. Table files should not be formatted as tables, but as column text blocks (using tabs to separate columns). Authors should use Arial 10 points, no boldface.
2. Authors should submit figures (graphs, charts, illustrations, etc.) in Excel, if possible, or the original graphics application, and not as embedded files in MS Word. Photos/images should have a resolution of 300 dpi. Figures should not be smaller than 5.5 by 8.5 inches. Figures should be one to a sheet. Authors should use at least 0.5-thick pt. lines for graphs, boxes, etc., in figures.
3. Authors should make sure that no objects (graphs or charts) are embedded between text blocks. Photo files are also accepted in the following electronic file formats: jpeg, tif, and gif. File name and type of file must be indicated.